

REGIONAL ANALYSIS OF INSECURITY AND THE CRISIS OF PUBLIC ORDER IN NIGERIA: MEASURING THROUGH THE LENS OF RELATIVE DEPRIVATION THEORY

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Abstract

Nigeria continues to grapple with persistent and regionally varied security challenges, ranging from insurgency, militancy and separatist violence to banditry and communal conflicts largely driven by perceived marginalisation, institutional failure and uneven development, thereby threatening public order and national cohesion. This paper examined the regional analysis of insecurity and the crisis of public order across Nigeria's six geopolitical zones, through the lens of Ted Robert Gurr's Relative Deprivation Theory. It employed a qualitative, historically grounded survey method using secondary sources and thematic-content analysis. The findings revealed that insecurity in Nigeria manifests differently across the geopolitical zones and often rooted in perceptions of socio-political exclusion, economic marginalisation, environmental degradation and historical grievances. From militancy and oil-related criminality in the South-South, IPOB-led separatist agitation in the South East, to terrorism, banditry, kidnapping, herdsman-farmers conflict and communal clashes in the North and South West regions, the persistence of insecurity reflects both structural failures and widespread feelings of relative deprivation. The paper argued that perceived inequalities and unmet expectations, rather than objective poverty alone, serve as primary drivers of public disorder. The failure of the Nigerian state to equitably deliver governance dividends has led to the proliferation of non-state actors, alternative security formations and widespread civil unrest, thereby eroding public trust and weakening state legitimacy. This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge by providing a regionally disaggregated analysis of insecurity in Nigeria and demonstrating the applicability of Relative Deprivation Theory in explaining the psychological and structural underpinnings of violence. It offers a conceptual framework that bridges socio-economic

realities with behavioural outcomes, enriching interdisciplinary discourse on security and governance. Future research should adopt mixed-methods and comparative approaches to explore the intersection of governance quality, youth political engagement and regional conflict dynamics.

Keywords: *Public Order, Insecurity, Crisis, Regional Analysis, Relative Deprivation Theory*

Introduction

Globally, rising insecurity has become a profound challenge, undermining the stability of nation-states, disrupting socio-economic development and eroding public confidence in the capacity and legitimacy of governments. From terrorist insurgencies to organised crime and civil unrest, insecurity not only jeopardises human safety but also weakens the foundations of democratic governance and economic growth (Salihu & Shodunke, 2024). In particular, the proliferation of non-state armed groups, the increasing frequency of attacks on civilians and the expansion of transnational criminal networks have all contributed to a growing climate of fear, uncertainty and instability in many parts of the world (Asangausung, Abang, Udousoro, Oko & Okon, 2024)

Across the African continent, these challenges have taken on region-specific dimensions. Violent extremism, separatist agitations, banditry and communal conflicts have emerged as dominant security threats, destabilising local communities and overwhelming fragile state institutions. Brown *et al.* (2024) notes that the inability of several African governments to effectively respond to these threats has further deepened political disillusionment, fuelled cycles of violence and triggered humanitarian crises. These security challenges are often exacerbated by poverty, youth unemployment, poor governance and competition over scarce resources, especially in ethnically or religiously diverse societies (Mboho & Asangausung, 2024).

Within the West African subregion, Nigeria presents a particularly complex security landscape. As Africa's most populous country and largest economy, Nigeria has experienced a convergence of internal and external security threats, ranging from Boko Haram insurgency in the North East and banditry in the North West, to militant oil-related criminality in the South-South and separatist agitations in the South East. Chibueze (2023) and Nwangwu (2023) observed that the South East, once regarded as a zone of relative peace, now experiences intensified insecurity linked to the activities of the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) and its armed wing, the Eastern Security Network (ESN). These groups' actions, including attacks on state institutions and enforced sit-at-home orders, have disrupted economic life, while state repression has aggravated public distrust in federal authority (Nduba *et al.*, 2024; Ifegwu & Ethel, 2022). In particular, Abba *et al.* (2023) demonstrated that IPOB's Monday lockdowns significantly affect income generation and business activity, with grave consequences for regional development.

In the South West, the proliferation of violent crimes, including kidnapping and cultism, has prompted the establishment of the Western Nigeria Security Network, popularly known as Amotekun. As revealed in studies by Awotayo *et al.* (2023), Ayiboye (2023) and Dogi *et al.* (2024), Amotekun has emerged as a community-driven response to rising insecurity and public dissatisfaction with centralised policing. However, operational limitations such as restrictions on the use of arms and jurisdictional ambiguities continue to

constrain its effectiveness (Asangausung *et al.*, 2024; Bassey *et al.*, 2024). Oyinloye *et al.* (2023), through spatial mapping, further confirmed that violent crime hotspots persist across the zone, particularly in Lagos, Ogun and Ondo States, driven largely by unemployment and resource competition.

These crises are regionally distinct in their manifestations but share common root causes, including perceived marginalisation, historical grievances, structural inequalities and the deteriorating legitimacy of the state (Asangausung & Brown, 2025). The fragmentation of state authority, the inadequate provision of public goods and widespread perceptions of injustice have created fertile ground for the rise of armed non-state actors who exploit grievances for political and economic gain. Consequently, Nigeria's security challenges not only threaten national unity and democratic consolidation but also have broader implications for regional stability and development in West Africa (Essoh *et al.*, 2025).

Despite the growing body of regional studies, most existing literature isolates regional security crises rather than examining their interconnections or shared structural roots. What remains under-theorised is the extent to which perceptions of deprivation and exclusion, rather than objective poverty alone fuel unrest across Nigeria's zones. Relative Deprivation Theory, which emphasises the discontent that arises when individuals or groups perceive a gap between expected and actual conditions (Gurr, 1970), offers a robust lens through which to unify and interpret these regionally diverse manifestations of insecurity. This study addressed the existing gap by applying this theory to interrogate the regional dynamics of crime and public disorder, highlighting the shared psychological and structural grievances that undermine national cohesion and stability. Against this backdrop, this paper interrogated the challenges to public order in Nigeria by examining the regional manifestations, patterns and socio-political drivers of crime and insecurity across the six geopolitical zones through the lens of Relative Deprivation Theory.

Literature Review

Boko Haram Insurgency in the North East Region of Nigeria

The reviewed literature on the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria's North East region reveals a comprehensive yet fragmented understanding of the conflict's multidimensional consequences. Salihu and Shodunke (2024) provided an in-depth account of the vulnerabilities faced by children orphaned by Boko Haram's attacks, emphasising their exposure to exploitation, armed recruitment and precarious living conditions. Similarly, Adesote and Ajayi (2021) highlighted the regional and international ramifications of the insurgency, showing how the violence transformed Nigeria into a refugee-producing country and compelled multilateral responses across West Africa. Etor and Asekhauno (2024) examined the ideological and structural enablers of insurgency, including religious indoctrination and porous borders, while documenting the profound socioeconomic tolls such as rising poverty, unemployment and food insecurity. Idowu *et al.* (2021) added an educational dimension to this body of work, demonstrating the insurgency's devastating impact on learning environments, including the destruction of infrastructure, loss of personnel and long-term disruptions to educational continuity.

Despite the richness of these studies, a notable gap persists in their failure to integrate the psychological and perceptual dimensions of insecurity, particularly the underlying feelings of political and economic marginalisation that feed discontent and rebellion. Most of

the literature review emphasise the outcomes of violence rather than the socio-psychological triggers that sustain it. Furthermore, while the studies provide useful sectoral analyses; on education, refugees, child welfare, or governance, they fall short of offering a regionally comparative framework that situates the North East within Nigeria's broader geopolitical security landscape. This gap leaves unanswered questions about why different regions manifest unique patterns of insecurity and how localised grievances converge with national dysfunctions to undermine public order.

This current research addresses the gap by applying Relative Deprivation Theory as a unifying analytical framework to interrogate how perceived injustice, marginalisation and failed expectations contribute to insecurity across Nigeria's six geopolitical zones. By drawing from the reviewed literature, the study anchors its analysis of the North East within a broader conceptual architecture that allows for comparison with other regions such as the South East and South West, where separatism and criminality take different forms but emerge from similarly perceived grievances. In doing so, the study shifts the discourse from episodic accounts of violence to a more systemic and comparative examination of insecurity as a function of relational discontent.

The implications of this approach are both theoretical and practical. Theoretically, it enriches the understanding of insecurity in Nigeria by connecting material and psychological dimensions of violence. Practically, it signals to policymakers the need for region-sensitive strategies that address not only physical threats but also the perceptions of exclusion and injustice that fuel unrest. In summary, while existing studies have laid an important foundation by detailing the manifestations of Boko Haram's violence, this research extends the conversation by offering a comparative and theory-driven analysis of public disorder, thereby contributing to a more nuanced and actionable understanding of Nigeria's insecurity crisis.

Banditry and ISWAP Activities in the North West Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria

The literature on banditry and insurgent violence in Nigeria's North West region reveals a robust but segmented analysis of the security crisis. Kleffmann *et al.* (2024) provided empirical insights into the far-reaching consequences of banditry on the everyday lives of residents in Katsina, Zamfara and Sokoto, particularly regarding physical safety, economic survival and access to education. Their findings confirmed that bandit attacks have become routine and deeply disruptive, leading to displacement and fear. Ebonine (2022) further extended the analysis by situating the rise of banditry within a broader ideological and educational context, suggesting that its links to extremist groups like Boko Haram and ISWAP are not merely strategic but also ideological, with an expressed goal of dismantling Western education as part of a larger Islamisation project.

Similarly, Nsiegebe and Gabriel (2024) emphasised the role of Nigeria's porous borders in sustaining banditry, revealing how the weak control of transboundary movement facilitates arms smuggling and the movement of criminal elements. Atutbi (2022) added a spatial and structural dimension to the discourse, highlighting the role of under-governed forested regions, economic disenfranchisement and institutional failure in enabling the spread of banditry, while Ogidigben and Otite (2022) offered a theoretical justification for the phenomenon using the Instrumental Theory of Violence, asserting that banditry in the North West represents a strategic means through which marginalised or insurgent actors attempt to renegotiate their positions within Nigeria's socio-political framework.

Despite these diverse contributions, a key gap in the literature lies in the lack of an

integrative framework that connects the psychological perceptions of deprivation to the structural and geopolitical variations of insecurity in Nigeria. The studies reviewed largely describe the symptoms and structural drivers of banditry, but they do not fully engage with how local actors interpret their socioeconomic conditions and respond to perceived marginalisation. As such, they do not sufficiently account for the role of perception, particularly the gap between expectations and reality in shaping collective behaviour and sustaining insecurity. Moreover, while some studies touch on connections between banditry and other forms of violence (such as Boko Haram insurgency or herder-farmer clashes), few adopt a comparative lens that situates the North West experience within the national landscape of public disorder.

This current research addresses these omissions by employing Relative Deprivation Theory as a conceptual lens to examine how perceived inequalities and frustrated expectations drive different forms of insecurity across Nigeria's six geopolitical zones. It fills the analytical gap by integrating the psychological and material dimensions of violence, demonstrating that banditry in the North West is not only a consequence of weak institutions and structural neglect but also of subjective feelings of exclusion and injustice. By applying this framework across zones, the research enables a more coherent understanding of why violence takes distinct forms in different regions, even when driven by shared frustrations. The implications are significant: understanding insecurity through the lens of relative deprivation reveals the limitations of purely militarised responses and emphasises the need for developmental and governance-oriented strategies that are responsive to regional grievances. In conclusion, while previous studies offer valuable data and interpretations on banditry in the North West, this research advances the discourse by linking regional patterns of insecurity to a broader national crisis of legitimacy and failed expectations, thereby contributing to more context-sensitive and theoretically grounded policy interventions.

Herdsman-Farmers Clashes in the North Central Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria

The reviewed literature on herdsman-farmers clashes in Nigeria's North Central region reveals a complex and deepening crisis with serious implications for public order, human security and national cohesion. Ajodo-Adebanjoko and Nwafor (2024) emphasised the widespread displacement, loss of livelihoods and humanitarian emergencies triggered by the conflict, particularly in states like Benue, Plateau, Nasarawa and Kogi. They observed that the frequency and intensity of these clashes have disrupted local economies and heightened national security concerns. Mustapha (2023), using qualitative methods, highlighted that cattle-induced destruction of farmland and retaliatory attacks by host communities have degraded social relations and exacerbated tensions between farming and herding populations, leading to repeated cycles of violence, economic loss and community breakdown.

Building on this, Okpeh *et al.* (2021) focused on the adverse effects of the conflict on human security. Their findings showed that the conflict not only causes fatalities and forced migration but also induces food insecurity, economic destitution and inter-communal dislocation. Similarly, Baba and Abeysinghe (2017) linked the persistence of these clashes to deeper structural issues such as state failure, ineffective local governance and the absence of credible conflict resolution mechanisms. These systemic failures, rather than mere competition over land, have allowed the crisis to fester unchecked, resulting in growing humanitarian challenges and weakening state legitimacy.

Furthermore, Babatunde and Ibnouf (2024) introduced a transnational dimension by

comparing the conflict in Nigeria with that of Sudan, noting that government and local actors often intensify conflict through the politicisation of peacebuilding and resource allocation. Their study underlines how governance structures can unintentionally deepen grievances by enabling unequal access to power and resources, further reinforcing perceptions of marginalisation and exclusion. Despite the rich insights provided by these studies, there remains a significant theoretical and analytical gap in understanding the psychological and perceptual dimensions of the conflict. Most of the literature focuses on structural causes such as environmental degradation, governance failure and livelihood insecurity without adequately exploring how perceptions of injustice, exclusion and loss shape the behaviour of affected communities. These perceptions are essential to understanding why similar conditions in different areas produce varying levels of violence.

This current study addresses the gap by employing Gurr's Relative Deprivation Theory to explore how perceived inequalities, unmet expectations and frustrated socio-economic aspirations fuel insecurity in the North Central zone. Rather than viewing the crisis solely as a material or territorial contest, the study investigates how the feeling of being unfairly treated or disadvantaged relative to others, especially in terms of access to land, protection and government support drives the radicalisation of actors and sustains cycles of violence.

By situating the North Central conflict within a broader theoretical framework and comparing it across Nigeria's geopolitical zones, this research advances a more holistic understanding of public disorder. It bridges the gap between structural and perceptual explanations of insecurity and highlights the need for multi-level, context-sensitive responses. Ultimately, the study demonstrates that effective interventions must address not only the objective material causes of conflict but also the subjective experiences of deprivation that shape communal relations and security outcomes in Nigeria.

Militancy and Oil-Related Criminality in the South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria

The reviewed literature on militancy and oil-related criminality in Nigeria's South-South geopolitical zone highlights a persistent cycle of deprivation, resistance and insecurity rooted in the political economy of oil extraction and state neglect. Enyidah-OkeyOrdu (2017) argues that despite the Niger Delta's critical role in sustaining the national economy through oil revenues, its communities remain deeply impoverished, environmentally degraded and socially marginalised. This state of systemic neglect, compounded by the exploitative operations of multinational oil corporations, has provoked militant responses aimed at compelling the government and oil companies to address long-standing developmental and compensatory demands. These militant activities, while initially rooted in socio-political agitation, have gradually escalated into broader security threats.

Egbe (2025) complements this analysis by demonstrating how socioeconomic disparities, especially those related to income and education, have led to increased criminal behaviour in the region. His findings, grounded in both Relative Deprivation and General Strain theories, reinforce the idea that inequality and perceived marginalisation are central to understanding youth violence and militancy in oil-producing communities. This is echoed in Ezirim's (2018) study, which highlights how the exclusion of local populations from oil benefits has fostered a proliferation of criminal activities such as oil bunkering, pipeline vandalism and piracy, thereby posing severe threats to national security.

Further deepening the discourse, Agbai and Ogbuku (2022) and Okoli and David (2016) traced the evolution of militancy from a quest for socio-economic justice to a

structure of organised criminality. Their findings underscore a shift in the political economy of resistance, where militant groups, originally formed as instruments of regional advocacy, have transformed into actors in a thriving underground economy sustained by oil theft, extortion and violent disruption. These studies point to the emergence of a new social class driven by the proceeds of criminal enterprise, thereby normalising insecurity and undermining both governance and developmental efforts.

Despite the depth of these studies, they predominantly focus on the material and structural drivers of insecurity such as environmental degradation, resource control and governance failures, while overlooking the perceptual and psychological dimensions of grievance that underpin many of these conflicts. This current research fills that gap by applying Relative Deprivation Theory to examine how perceived injustices, exclusion and unfulfilled expectations fuel insecurity and criminality in the South-South. Rather than merely cataloguing economic inequalities, it interrogates how feelings of being unfairly treated despite regional resource wealth intensify discontent and shape both militant ideologies and community attitudes toward the state.

By synthesising existing literature and embedding it within a broader theoretical framework, this study contributes a more holistic understanding of the security challenges in the South-South region. It offers insights into how criminality and militancy are sustained not only by structural conditions but also by collective perceptions of deprivation, thereby broadening the scope for policy responses. This perspective enables a more nuanced analysis of public disorder in oil-rich regions and provides a foundation for designing interventions that are not only responsive to material needs but also to the subjective realities of affected communities.

Diverse Security Threats in the South West Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria

The reviewed literature on the South West geopolitical zone reveals a complex and evolving security landscape marked by the interplay of violent crime, kidnapping, herder-farmer clashes and community-led security initiatives. Scholars such as Awotayo *et al.* (2023) and Dogi *et al.* (2024) highlight the emergence and operational efficacy of the Western Nigeria Security Network (Amotekun Corps) as a localised security response to the growing insecurity in the region. Empirical findings suggest that Amotekun has gained public confidence due to its swift responses, close ties with local communities and contributions to reducing crime in Osun and Ondo states. However, the challenges faced by Amotekun, particularly regarding the prohibition on carrying sophisticated arms due to federal policies, limit its effectiveness in countering heavily armed criminal groups.

Further studies, such as Ayiboye (2023), emphasise the network's intelligence-gathering role and its collaboration with formal security institutions, indicating its strategic value within a broader hybrid security framework. Nonetheless, as noted by Alo (2023), the region, once considered among the most peaceful in Nigeria, now grapples with increasing incidences of kidnapping, often linked to ritual practices, ransom-seeking and retaliatory violence. These developments have negatively affected investment confidence and the region's economic stability.

In addition, Oyinloye *et al.* (2023) used geospatial and spatio-temporal analysis to trace violent crime hotspots across the six South Western states, revealing that armed robbery, assassination, cultism and herder-farmer conflicts are widespread, with major incidents clustered around urban highways and forested areas. Unemployment and land-use conflicts emerge as key triggers, while consequences include social disintegration,

displacement and infrastructure destruction. The mapping of these hotspots not only quantifies the spatial reach of insecurity but also reinforces the need for decentralised and targeted crime prevention strategies. Despite the growing body of work on the role of Amotekun and rising insecurity in the South West, there remains a theoretical gap in understanding how perceptions of marginalisation and unmet socio-political expectations fuel these regional dynamics. While previous studies have richly documented the operational and structural dimensions of crime and security responses, few have engaged with the psychological undercurrents of insecurity, particularly the subjective experiences of relative deprivation among affected populations.

This study addresses that gap by applying Relative Deprivation Theory to explain how perceived inequities such as exclusion from national security discourse, limited state responsiveness and growing regional victimisation, contribute to the escalation of insecurity in the South West. By grounding regional insecurity in the broader socio-psychological context of perceived injustice, the study not only advances the academic discourse on Nigeria's public order crisis but also opens new avenues for policy that are sensitive to both the material and emotional realities of affected communities.

In conclusion, while the South West has responded innovatively to the rising tide of insecurity through the establishment of Amotekun and increased community collaboration, the persistence of violent crime, kidnapping and communal conflict reveals deeper issues of structural inequality, institutional inadequacy and perceived marginalisation. This research situates these challenges within the framework of relative deprivation, thereby contributing a more nuanced and explanatory lens to the ongoing discourse on regional security and public order in Nigeria.

IPOB and ESN Activities in the South East Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria

The reviewed literature on the South East geopolitical zone highlights a multidimensional and escalating security crisis largely driven by the activities of the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) and its militant wing, the Eastern Security Network (ESN), as well as broader state responses marked by repression and militarisation. Ifegwu and Ethel (2022) argue that perceived marginalisation, militarised state responses and systemic injustice are at the root of insecurity in the South East, noting how these conditions undermine sustainable development by eroding trust in institutions and deepening popular disillusionment. Similarly, Chibueze (2023) stresses how the region, once considered among the most stable in the country, has witnessed a marked deterioration in security, characterised by IPOB-led agitation, attacks by “unknown gunmen,” reprisals by security forces and the rise of kidnapping and violence by other non-state actors, including killer herdsmen.

Other scholars focus on the socio-economic implications of IPOB's separatist strategies, particularly the recurring sit-at-home orders. Nduba *et al.* (2024) show that these enforced civil shutdowns have disrupted educational, commercial and transportation systems, severely affecting livelihoods across the region. This aligns with the findings of Abba *et al.* (2023), who used empirical data to demonstrate that these strategies have significantly curtailed economic activities, with daily income earners bearing the brunt of the losses. The studies reveal that rather than advancing the cause of self-determination, the sit-at-home orders have increasingly burdened the same communities they claim to defend.

Moreover, Nwangwu (2023) traces the evolution of IPOB's tactics, arguing that state repression has catalysed the group's shift from civil disobedience to armed struggle. His findings suggest that excessive force, arbitrary arrests, proscription and extrajudicial tactics

employed by the Nigerian state may not only be counterproductive but have intensified rather than mitigated separatist sentiment. This reinforces a growing consensus in the literature that the security situation in the South East cannot be understood without acknowledging the legacy of political exclusion, historical grievances and aggressive state securitisation. Despite the richness of these insights, a significant gap exists in the literature regarding a comprehensive, theory-driven explanation of how perceived marginalisation fuels insecurity in the region. While the reviewed studies document the impacts and surface causes of unrest, few engage explicitly with theoretical frameworks that connect these patterns of insecurity with deeper feelings of deprivation and socio-political alienation.

This current research addresses that gap by adopting Relative Deprivation Theory to analyse how the persistent sense of exclusion, politically, economically and symbolically shapes the South East's security crisis. It investigates the psychological and structural dimensions of insecurity, arguing that beyond physical violence, the perception of being denied access to power and opportunity within the Nigerian federation plays a central role in fuelling unrest.

In conclusion, the literature establishes that insecurity in the South East stems from a complex interplay of separatist agitation, harsh state repression and economic dislocation. However, the absence of a theoretical lens that ties these symptoms to underlying grievances has limited the development of nuanced policy responses.

Theoretical Framework

Relative Deprivation Theory

This paper was guided by the assumptions of Ted Robert Gurr's Relative Deprivation Theory developed in 1970. However, its roots can be traced earlier to Samuel A. Stouffer and Walter Runciman, who laid the foundational concepts in their respective studies of social behaviour and inequality. Relative Deprivation Theory posits that individuals or groups experience feelings of discontent and resentment when they perceive a discrepancy between their expected socio-economic or political conditions and their actual realities. This sense of deprivation is not necessarily absolute, but relative, people may not be poor in objective terms, but if they believe others in similar conditions are better off or that they have been unfairly treated, it breeds frustration and potential aggression.

Major Arguments

- The main argument of relative deprivation theory is that conflict is not merely a passing social event but an inseparable part of the human experience.
- Conflict has its own foundations in people's mind.
- People or community who feel deprived of some good(s) or resource(s) tend to conflict.
- Individuals or community who are lacking some good, service, or comfort are more likely to unleash an armed conflict to improve their material conditions.
- Proponents of this theory have not focused attention on violent conflict, per se, rather, they study episodes of political violence and revolution.
- In his study of 114 countries, Gurr found relative deprivation and inequality as the major cause for the manifestation of conflict and political violence.
- Ted Gurr (1970) states that his research is concerned with political violence – “all collective attacks within a political community against the political regime, its, actors ... or its policies”.
- Gurr formulates his notion of relative deprivation by linking expectations with

capabilities and states that violence is likely to develop in a society where a gap between actual and potential exists on a wide scale.

- Gurr states, a perceived discrepancy between men's value expectations and their value capabilities' can be understood as relative deprivation.
- Value expectations are goods and conditions of life to which people believe they are rightfully entitled' and 'value capabilities are the goods and conditions they are capable of attaining or maintaining', Gurr states.
- Relative deprivation may occur when expectations remain constant but capabilities decline; expectations increase but capabilities decline; and expectations increase while capabilities remain stable.
- Gurr argues that increasing expectations without increase in level of capabilities result in relative deprivation which manifests in violence.
- Thus, according to Gurr, violence derives from a high level of discontent caused from relative deprivation.

Application of Ted Robert Gurr's Relative Deprivation Theory

The theory of relative deprivation offers a compelling lens through which to interrogate the challenges to public order in Nigeria, particularly by examining the regional patterns of crime and insecurity across the six geopolitical zones. In the South East, the agitation by the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) and its armed wing, Eastern Security Network (ESN), is grounded in perceived political exclusion, economic marginalisation and historical grievances. The enforcement of sit-at-home orders and attacks on state institutions can be interpreted as manifestations of aspirational and progressive deprivation, where the Igbo population perceives a denial of their rightful stake in national governance.

In the South-South, militancy and oil-related criminality reflect a classic case of decremental deprivation. Communities in the Niger Delta have watched as their environment and means of livelihood deteriorated due to oil exploitation, while wealth generated from their resources is channelled elsewhere. This deprivation has fuelled militancy, vandalism and illegal bunkering as forms of protest and survival. In the North East, Boko Haram insurgency is partly rooted in perceptions of socio-economic abandonment, lack of educational opportunities and inequality in political representation. For many youths recruited by Boko Haram, insurgency is seen as a vehicle to correct what they perceive as a moral and developmental injustice. In the North Central and South West, the herdsman-farmer clashes and rising banditry and kidnapping are driven by deteriorating resource access, competition over land and unemployment. As expectations of security, economic opportunity and justice are unmet, communities turn to violence either as self-defence or as a form of economic sustenance. The North West also exhibits symptoms of aspirational deprivation. With rising levels of poverty, illiteracy and youth unemployment in the region, banditry has become both a rebellion against the state and a desperate economic option for survival.

Across all zones, the perceived failure of the Nigerian state to equitably deliver the dividends of governance, security, justice, development and representation has created a climate where public order is constantly challenged by criminality, violence and civil unrest. Relative deprivation explains why violence persists even in regions that receive federal attention, because perception, not just reality, drives action.

Criticisms

While Relative Deprivation Theory is widely applicable and insightful, it is not without criticisms. Scholars have pointed out that the theory tends to overemphasise the role of perception and fails to adequately explain why not all individuals or groups who feel deprived resort to violence. It has also been critiqued for under-theorising structural and institutional factors such as weak governance, corruption and impunity, which often play a decisive role in shaping conflict dynamics. Moreover, the theory does not fully account for the influence of political elites or external actors who may manipulate public grievances for personal or strategic gain. Additionally, it is sometimes considered too broad or abstract, lacking the necessary specificity to address the complex interplay of regional, ethnic and religious factors that characterise multi-diverse societies like Nigeria.

Justification

Despite its acknowledged limitations, Relative Deprivation Theory offers a compelling and contextually appropriate framework for analysing the multidimensional nature of insecurity and public disorder in Nigeria. It provides a socio-psychological lens that connects individual and group behaviour to broader patterns of perceived injustice, inequality and exclusion. This theoretical perspective helps to explain why different regions of the country manifest distinct forms of violence, ranging from secessionist agitation and militancy to banditry and communal clashes based on their unique experiences of marginalisation and frustrated expectations.

The theory's emphasis on perceived deprivation, rather than objective poverty alone, resonates strongly with the Nigerian context, where perceptions of unfair treatment, unfulfilled political promises and structural imbalances often drive unrest. Its applicability to both non-violent expressions of dissent, such as sit-at-home orders and violent confrontations, including insurgency and oil bunkering, makes it particularly useful for a comprehensive interrogation of Nigeria's security landscape.

Materials and Methods

This study employed a historical survey method to examine the challenges to public order in Nigeria, focusing on the dynamics of crime and insecurity across the six geopolitical zones. It adopted a qualitative approach, given the study's objective to understand the contextual, structural and perceptual dimensions of insecurity through interpretive analysis rather than empirical measurement. Data were sourced exclusively from secondary materials, including scholarly articles, academic theses, policy documents, government reports and credible media publications. Materials were selected purposively based on their relevance to regional security dynamics in Nigeria, particularly literature published between 2019 and 2024 that addressed phenomena such as separatist agitations, insurgency, militancy, communal clashes and organised criminality.

The analysis relied on thematic-content analysis, which allowed the researcher to identify, interpret and synthesise recurring themes across different geopolitical contexts. This method enabled the extraction of nuanced insights into the causes, manifestations and consequences of insecurity, as well as the responses of state and non-state actors. The study was theoretically anchored on Relative Deprivation Theory, which posits that perceived disparities between expectations and actual conditions can generate discontent, resentment and ultimately violent or anti-social behaviour. This theoretical lens facilitated a deeper interrogation of how perceived marginalisation, inequality and exclusion have shaped

divergent expressions of insecurity across Nigeria.

The study was delimited to issues of public order within Nigeria's six geopolitical zones from 2020 to 2024. It did not involve primary fieldwork or direct human engagement. All data were ethically sourced and properly cited to ensure academic integrity. This methodological approach ensured a robust and contextually grounded analysis of Nigeria's multifaceted security challenges.

Results and Discussions

Boko Haram Insurgency in the North East Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria

The findings of this study underscore the persistent and multidimensional nature of insecurity in the North East region of Nigeria, particularly as shaped by the Boko Haram insurgency. Since its emergence in 2009, Boko Haram has not only redefined the character of violence in the region but has also systematically eroded the mechanisms of public order, governance and civil authority. Borno, Yobe and Adamawa States have been the epicentres of the insurgency, with devastating consequences for human security, economic stability and institutional resilience.

The insurgency, originally ideologically framed against Western education and secular governance, has evolved into a protracted armed conflict marked by mass killings, abductions, suicide bombings and territorial seizures. A significant turning point occurred with the 2016 splintering of Boko Haram and the emergence of the Islamic State West Africa Province (ISWAP), which has adopted a more calculated military and governance-oriented strategy. ISWAP's alignment with the broader Islamic State network has introduced new dynamics of transnational terrorism into the local conflict, further complicating security responses. This study found that the sustained presence of Boko Haram and ISWAP has led to the disintegration of civil administration in several parts of the region. In many rural and semi-urban communities, these groups have established parallel governance structures, collecting taxes, adjudicating disputes and delivering rudimentary social services. This directly challenges the Nigerian state's monopoly on legitimate violence and undermines its capacity to maintain public order.

The application of Relative Deprivation Theory to these findings is particularly instructive. As Gurr (1970) posited, violence becomes likely when there is a perceived disparity between expected and actual socio-political conditions. The socio-economic realities of the North East; chronic poverty, illiteracy, infrastructural decay and long-standing neglect have created a deep sense of marginalisation. This aspirational and decremental deprivation fuels resentment among the region's youth, many of whom view insurgency not only as a form of ideological expression but also as a viable economic and social alternative. The radicalisation and recruitment mechanisms employed by Boko Haram exploit these sentiments, offering identity, purpose and survival in exchange for allegiance.

Empirical support for these findings is provided by Salihu and Shodunke (2024), who highlighted the vulnerabilities of orphaned children affected by insurgency, including their exposure to exploitation, forced labour and violent extremism. Their qualitative study in Yobe State reveals that insecurity has created a cycle of generational trauma and dislocation, further destabilising communities. Similarly, Adesote and Ajayi (2021) examined the regional and transnational consequences of Boko Haram's activities, linking Nigeria's refugee crises and diplomatic tensions with neighboring countries to the sustained insurgency. These outcomes reflect both the physical and geopolitical implications of the

insurgency.

In addition, Etor and Asekhauno (2024) identified religious indoctrination and porous borders as significant enabling factors in the North East, contributing to the persistent threat of terrorism. Their analysis emphasises the socio-economic fallout, including increased poverty, unemployment and food insecurity, which reinforce the sense of deprivation experienced by local populations. Idowu *et al.* (2021) also provided compelling evidence of the insurgency's deleterious effects on education and economic development. The destruction of schools and the loss of skilled manpower due to displacement and insecurity have had long-term implications on human capital development in the region. The disruption of public services and economic livelihoods has further entrenched a humanitarian crisis, with over two million internally displaced persons (IDPs) relying on inadequate relief efforts. The collapse of infrastructure and the militarisation of civilian spaces have bred mistrust between communities and state actors, especially security forces accused of human rights violations. This erosion of trust not only impedes counter-insurgency efforts but also weakens the legitimacy of the state.

Theoretically, these developments validate the assumptions of Relative Deprivation Theory by demonstrating how perceived or real inequality, when unmet by institutional redress, can produce violent outcomes. The insurgency persists not merely because of ideological motivations, but because of the socio-political conditions that foster perceptions of abandonment and marginalisation. Gurr's typology of deprivation is evident in the frustration of youths unable to access education or employment (aspirational), in the loss of previously enjoyed security or livelihoods (decremental) and in rising expectations unmet by government intervention (progressive).

However, this explanation must be situated within a broader structural context. While Relative Deprivation Theory captures the psychological motivations for insurgency, it must be supplemented with structural analyses that consider state failure, elite manipulation and regional inequality. Nevertheless, the theory remains valuable for understanding the emotive and perceptual dimensions of public disorder in the North East.

In conclusion, the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria's North East geopolitical zone exemplifies the collapse of public order driven by perceived injustice, institutional failure and prolonged socio-economic deprivation. The persistence of insecurity in the region demands not only military responses but also holistic interventions that address root causes through governance reform, youth empowerment, inclusive development and post-conflict reconstruction. Without such integrated strategies, the region remains vulnerable to cycles of violence and fragmentation, threatening national security and regional stability.

Banditry and ISWAP Activities in the North West Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria

The findings from this study revealed that the security crisis in Nigeria's North West geopolitical zone was driven by the rise of armed banditry and the growing presence of jihadist groups such as the Islamic State West Africa Province (ISWAP). States including Zamfara, Katsina, Kaduna, Sokoto, Kebbi and parts of Niger had become hotbeds of violent criminality, where the line between organised crime and insurgency had blurred significantly. What initially began as localised herder-farmer disputes over land and water had escalated into large-scale militarised violence, sustained by socio-economic hardship and institutional decay.

This situation aligned with Ted Gurr's (1970) Relative Deprivation Theory, particularly the notions of aspirational and progressive deprivation, which explained how

rising expectations of state protection, justice and economic opportunity had been consistently unmet, resulting in widespread frustration and aggression. Youths, disillusioned by poverty, unemployment and systemic neglect, were increasingly drawn into bandit gangs as both a means of survival and a form of protest. As Ogidigben and Otite (2022) argued, the convergence of bandit groups with jihadist factions such as ISWAP reflected a strategic evolution of violence into a tool for asserting control in the face of absent governance.

Empirical studies, such as that by Kleffmann *et al.* (2024), confirmed the devastating impact of banditry on livelihoods, education and mobility across states like Katsina and Zamfara. These attacks had become so frequent that many communities had adapted by negotiating with armed groups, effectively replacing state authority with private arrangements for security. Ebonine (2022) noted that the education sector had been severely affected, with the abduction of students serving not only as a source of ransom but also as a jihadist tactic to delegitimise Western education—echoing earlier Boko Haram strategies in the North East.

The region's porous borders with the Niger Republic and the limited capacity of Nigerian security institutions were found to have exacerbated the crisis. Nsiegebe and Gabriel (2024) highlighted how these ungoverned borderlands allowed for the influx of arms, insurgents and contraband, further destabilising the region. Local populations, observing improvements in other regions and expecting similar development, experienced progressive deprivation as their own conditions deteriorated, deepening their alienation and eroding trust in the state.

Environmental and infrastructural conditions also played a role. Forest belts like Rugu and Kamuku provided safe havens for criminal and insurgent groups, enabling them to evade state surveillance and control. Atutbi (2022) linked the ungoverned nature of these zones to the sustainability of banditry, pointing out how attacks on markets, farms and trade routes intensified food insecurity and economic collapse; consequences that fed further into cycles of deprivation and violence. While Relative Deprivation Theory provided a strong lens through which to understand the psychological and social roots of this violence, it did not fully capture the complexity of the crisis. Other theoretical insights, such as Instrumental Violence Theory and Weak State Theory, offered valuable complements. Ogidigben and Otite (2022) explained how violence had been used strategically by both state and non-state actors to achieve political and economic ends, while Nsiegebe and Gabriel (2024) underscored how state fragility and corruption had allowed violence to flourish unchecked. In conclusion, the study demonstrated that the North West's security crisis stemmed from overlapping layers of deprivation, aspirational, progressive and decremental—deepened by state failure, ideological extremism and socio-economic collapse. Banditry had evolved beyond criminality into a broader insurgent threat, requiring a holistic and proactive response. This included not only military action but also long-term investments in governance, youth empowerment, education, border control and social justice, in line with the explanatory frameworks offered by both Gurr's Relative Deprivation Theory and the broader literature on political violence and state fragility.

Herdsmen-Farmers Clashes in the North Central Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria

The conflict between herdsmen and farmers in Nigeria's North Central region represents a deeply rooted challenge to public order, evolving from land disputes into a protracted crisis driven by environmental degradation, economic strain and ethno-religious tensions. While desertification and demographic pressures fuel resource competition,

identity politics and weak governance structures exacerbate grievances. Relative Deprivation Theory offers a useful lens for understanding how mutual perceptions of injustice among farmers and herders, ranging from lack of security and economic opportunity to political marginalisation—rive cycles of violence.

Literature reviewed, including Ajodo-Adebanjoko and Nwafor (2024), Mustapha (2023) and Babatunde and Ibnouf (2024), supports this view, illustrating the collapse of rural livelihoods, the erosion of social trust and the failure of both state and traditional mechanisms to mediate disputes effectively. Militarization, institutional failure and the absence of inclusive land and resource policies have transformed local grievances into national insecurity. In sum, the herders-farmers conflict is sustained not only by material deprivation but also by a deep-seated sense of exclusion, which Relative Deprivation Theory helps illuminate.

Militancy and Oil-Related Criminality in the South-South Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria

The findings from this study revealed that militancy and oil-related criminality in Nigeria's South-South region were deeply entrenched in socio-economic and environmental injustices, rooted in historical marginalisation and persistent governance failures. Despite the implementation of the Presidential Amnesty Programme (PAP), insecurity not only persisted but evolved into more sophisticated and criminally organised networks driven by unresolved grievances. Using Relative Deprivation Theory (Gurr, 1970) as an interpretive lens, the study demonstrated how the disparity between the region's oil wealth and its underdeveloped communities fostered feelings of betrayal and resentment. This sentiment was particularly evident in the perceived erosion of anticipated benefits; what Gurr termed decremental deprivation, amid continuous environmental degradation and a lack of equitable development (Okoli & Atelhe, 2014).

The emergence of militant groups such as MEND initially represented a political response to socio-economic exclusion, as observed by Enyidah-OkeyOrdu (2017). However, the post-amnesty era witnessed the transformation of militancy into a structured criminal economy. Activities like artisanal refining and pipeline vandalism reflected aspirational deprivation, wherein youth and communities resorted to illicit economies after experiencing persistent exclusion from expected development opportunities (Ezirim, 2018). Scholars such as Okoli and David (2016) described this transformation as part of a broader trend of petro-rentierism, where conflict and resource control were commodified within a corrupt patronage system. This dynamic entrenched progressive deprivation, as rising expectations generated by partial government interventions were consistently undermined by enduring structural inequalities.

Egbe (2025) further attributed youth participation in petro-criminality to perceived social injustice and the lack of legitimate economic alternatives. His findings emphasised the growing frustration, particularly in response to the preferential treatment of ex-militants who were awarded lucrative security contracts. Environmental degradation, which remained a recurring issue in the literature, worsened poverty and reinforced the legitimacy of resistance, while militarised security responses, often carried out by co-opted ex-agitators further eroded rule of law and state credibility (Agbai & Ogbuku, 2022; Ikelegbe, 2011).

In sum, the study confirmed that militancy and oil-related crimes in the South-South were not mere acts of opportunistic criminality but manifestations of entrenched grievances stemming from socio-political exclusion, economic marginalisation and ecological decline. These conditions were compounded by institutional fragility, elite manipulation and the

collapse of environmental governance, resulting in a state of multidimensional deprivation that compromised livelihoods, public trust and national cohesion (Oyinloye *et al.*, 2023). Addressing these issues required a holistic and inclusive development strategy that moved beyond temporary appeasement to embrace environmental restoration, equitable governance and sustained community empowerment.

IPOB and ESN Activities in the South East Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria

The security crisis in Nigeria's South East is deeply tied to the activities of the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) and its paramilitary wing, the Eastern Security Network (ESN). Rooted in long-standing grievances over marginalisation and exclusion following the civil war, the IPOB movement evolved from peaceful agitation to militarised resistance with the creation of ESN in 2020. Framed within Relative Deprivation Theory, the conflict illustrates how perceived disparities between group expectations and lived realities such as underrepresentation in federal structures, infrastructural neglect and economic disparity fuel frustration and mobilise collective action.

The imposition of sit-at-home orders, often unofficially attributed to IPOB, emerged as a symbolic and coercive tool of protest, significantly disrupting economic and social life in the region. These disruptions, especially to SMEs, transport and education have deepened the region's socio-economic decline. As IPOB and ESN escalated confrontations with Nigerian security forces, the state's repressive responses, including arrests, militarisation and human rights abuses, further alienated the population and reinforced IPOB's narrative of state oppression.

Research by Ifegwu and Ethel (2022), Nwangwu (2023) and Abba *et al.* (2023) underscores how these dynamics have entrenched insecurity, fostered civil distrust and crippled local economies. While Relative Deprivation Theory helps explain the psychological and political dimensions of this unrest, it cannot alone account for structural failures like poor governance and elite manipulation that shape the conflict's persistence. In sum, the IPOB-ESN crisis transcends criminality; it reflects deep socio-political discontent that demands inclusive governance, institutional reform and sustained dialogue. Without these, cycles of violence and economic stagnation in the South East are likely to persist, threatening national cohesion.

Conclusion

This paper interrogated the challenges to public order in Nigeria by examining the patterns of insecurity across the six geopolitical zones, employing Relative Deprivation Theory as the analytical lens. The findings revealed that insecurity in Nigeria is regionally nuanced and often rooted in perceptions of socio-political exclusion, economic marginalisation, environmental degradation and historical grievances. From militancy and oil-related criminality in the South-South, IPOB-led separatist agitation in the South East, to banditry, kidnapping and communal clashes in the North and South West regions, the persistence of insecurity reflects both structural failures and widespread feelings of relative deprivation.

The paper argued that perceived inequalities and unmet expectations, rather than objective poverty alone, serve as primary drivers of public disorder. The failure of the Nigerian state to equitably deliver governance dividends has led to the proliferation of non-state actors, alternative security formations and widespread civil unrest, thereby eroding public trust and weakening state legitimacy. This study contributes to the existing body of

knowledge by providing a regionally disaggregated analysis of insecurity in Nigeria and demonstrating the applicability of Relative Deprivation Theory in explaining the psychological and structural underpinnings of violence. It offers a conceptual framework that bridges socio-economic realities with behavioural outcomes, enriching interdisciplinary discourse on security and governance. Future research should adopt mixed-methods and comparative approaches to explore the intersection of governance quality, youth political engagement and regional conflict dynamics. Longitudinal studies could also investigate the evolving strategies of state and non-state actors in managing public order and the long-term implications for national cohesion and democratic consolidation.

Recommendations

- i. The federal and state governments should implement region-specific development strategies that address the underlying drivers of insecurity, such as poverty, unemployment, environmental degradation and social exclusion. Particular attention should be given to neglected regions like the Niger Delta and the North East, ensuring equitable distribution of resources and opportunities.
- ii. The government must strengthen democratic institutions and ensure greater political inclusion of marginalised groups. Transparent leadership, fair resource allocation and justice system reforms are essential to rebuild public trust and reduce the perception of systemic injustice fuelling agitation and violence.
- iii. Security should be decentralised by integrating community policing and supporting regional initiatives such as the Amotekun Corps. These outfits should be institutionalized with clear legal backing, adequate training and oversight mechanisms to enhance their effectiveness without undermining national unity.
- iv. Security agencies should improve collaboration, intelligence gathering and rapid response to threats across state borders. A national security strategy that incorporates regional peculiarities is vital for coordinated and effective crime prevention.
- v. The state must prioritise dialogue with aggrieved groups such as IPOB and other militant factions, addressing legitimate grievances through peaceful negotiation and reintegration rather than through force alone, which has often escalated tensions.
- vi. Programmes that promote vocational training, entrepreneurship and civic responsibility among the youth can reduce their vulnerability to recruitment by criminal and insurgent groups. Education policies must be aligned with job market needs to ensure long-term socio-economic stability.
- vii. Immediate and sustained efforts must be made to clean up polluted environments in the South-South, especially in areas devastated by oil exploitation. This should be accompanied by fair compensation and infrastructural investment to rebuild affected communities.

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